

PILOT PLANT SCALE-UP TECHNIQUE

Aniket G.Karodade¹, Sunil S.Bhagat², Dr. Swati P.Deshmukh³, Aniket P. Wable⁴

¹Student Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Kondala Zamre, Washim 444505

²Assistant Professor Department of Industrial Pharmacy Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim

³Principal Shraddha Institute Of Pharmacy, Department of Pharmacology Kondala Zamre, Washim

⁴Student Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Kondala Zamre, Washim

ABSTRACT: Pilot plant scale-up technology is a part of the pharmaceutical industry that replaces the scale-up model for large-scale products by developing a reliable and efficient production process. Pilot plant scaling strategies regarding the amount of information will provide guidance for large-scale production, where they will play an important role. Responsibilities include personnel requirements, site requirements, review of raw materials, work equipment, production, GMP decisions and mixing, granulation, drying, compression, etc. General requirements for measurement, such as parameters such as. It plays an important role in development. Drug information. Pilot facilities are smaller than full production facilities. The facility, which is also a training facility, plans to conduct several clinical trials at the pilot site to provide its employees with the opportunity to refine and validate the process.

KEYWORDS: Pilot Plant, scale Up Techniques, Solid Dosage Form, Tablet, Drying

INTRODUCTION:

Pilot plant scale-up is a critical technique in the field of process engineering and manufacturing. It plays a pivotal role in the transition from laboratory experimentation to full-scale industrial production. This methodology involves the careful and systematic replication of a small-scale process within a controlled pilot plant environment, with the primary goal of assessing and optimizing its feasibility for large-scale production. Pilot plant scale-up is a fundamental bridge between research and commercialization, enabling companies to refine processes, validate product quality, and mitigate risks before making substantial investments in full-scale production facilities. In this discussion, we will delve into the principles, challenges, and significance of pilot plant scale-up as an essential stage in the development of new processes and products. Pilot plant expansion is an important process aimed at bridging the gap between laboratory testing and largescale production in chemical engineering and manufacturing. The technology is a cornerstone in the development and optimization of new products and processes, allowing engineers and scientists to evaluate the feasibility, effectiveness and efficiency of safely growing from small laboratories to commercial scale.

Scale-up cultivation is essentially a method, the optimization of the use of a concept or chemical by measuring it from the bench in the laboratory to the control center, to the center of the center. The main goal is to determine the possibilities of the process, identify and reduce difficulties or dangers, and work efficiently to achieve good production and cost. Pilot plant expansion process for pharmaceuticals, pharmaceuticals, food, etc. It covers a wide range of industries including: It involves numerous controls, from material selection and design to purchasing, safety procedures and environmental assessments. The success of this technology is important in reducing the risks associated with the transition to mass production, ensuring product quality and meeting regulatory requirements. In this introductory chapter, we explore the main concepts, methods and issues related to the expansion of pilot plants, paying attention to the words of plant strategies taken from the laboratory and turning them into truly useful business processes.

DEFINATIONS:

Plant:

It is place where the 5's like money, material, man, machine And method are brought together for the manufacturing of The product. **Pilot:**

It is the part of pharmaceutical industry where a lab scale Formula is transformed in to viable product by development Of liable and practical procedure of manufacture.

Scale up:

The art for designing of prototype using the data obtained from the pilot plant model

OBJECTIVES:

- To try the process on a model of proposed plant before Committing large sum of money on a production unit.
- To identify the critical feature of the process.
- Production and Process Information.
- Providing food production ideas and manufacturing techniques.
- Avoid scaling issues.

SCALE UP STEP:

Development and validation of processes and equipment Pilot plant scale-up is a process that involves several key steps in turning a pilot plant scale-up into a larger operation. The steps to establish a pilot plant are:

1. **Defining Goals and Procedures:** Clearly state the goals, objectives, and process for achieving success in October. What is your purpose? What are the key performance indicators?
2. **Feasibility only:** Look at the technical and financial feasibility of scaling up the process. Consider factors such as availability, cost, security and compatibility.
3. **Process Characterization:** Thoroughly understand the characteristics of a laboratory process, including its chemistry, kinetics, and potential limitations.
4. **Equipment Selection:** Select appropriate drive equipment that is similar to commercial equipment in functionality and capacity.
5. **Determining the amplification factor:** Calculate the amplification factor of the main process (such as temperature, pressure, flow rate and reaction time). Make sure these conditions are commensurate with the size increase.
6. **Procurement:** Purchasing the raw materials and equipment required for the pilot study. Be consistent and compatible with measuring instruments.
7. **Installation and Installation:** Assemble and install pilot scale equipment, instrumentation and control systems. Make sure safety precautions are taken.
8. **Best Practices:** Perform a preliminary test using the drive tool to ensure it can accurately repeat the testing procedure.
9. **Process Improvements:** Correct poor processes and conditions as needed to improve product quality, yield, and efficiency. This may involve several repetitions.
10. **Data Collection:** Collect data continuously throughout the evaluation process and monitor for significant and adverse changes.
11. **Product Testing:** Testing the quality and performance of products to ensure they meet requirements.
12. **Scale-Up Verification:** Verify that pilot-scale operations can produce representatives of all products at all times.
13. **Troubleshooting:** Resolve operational issues or problems that arise during testing and make necessary adjustments to equipment or procedures.
14. **Safety and compliance:** Ensure safe operations and compliance with all applicable laws and regulations throughout the pilot operation.
15. **Cost Analysis:** Evaluate the cost effectiveness of a pilot-scale operation and compare it to full-scale production costs.

GENERAL REQUIREMENTS:

Description of Responsibilities:

The responsible facility will be part of the R&D group with independent personnel. This arrangement aims to provide a Role of responsibility extending to formulation by other Formulators in the R&D process, thus giving the opportunity for model process independent Imitation Original working model. Alternatively, products created from the design Are completed and ready for production.

Required Personnel:

The qualifications required for a position in the organization are a combination of Good chemical knowledge and Technical knowledge, familiar to small and medium-sized businesses in the pharmaceutical industry. Employees need to have good verbal and written skills, and the ability to build relationships with others is also crucial.

Space Requirements:

Adequate space for the pilot equipment: Ensure there's enough room for the equipment required for your pilot-scale process, including reactors, pumps, tanks, and instrumentation Safety clearances: Follow safety guidelines and allow for appropriate clearances around equipment to ensure safe operation and maintenance Utility connections Space for utility connections such as electricity, water, gas, and ventilation is crucial for the operation of the pilot plant.

Storage and handling areas: Include areas for storing raw materials, intermediates, and finished products, as well as space for material handling and storage tanks Analytical and control areas: Allocate space for laboratories or control rooms where data can be monitored, collected, and analyzed.

Fig.1 Administration area

Management and data processing are important. Adequate office space and desks should be provided for researchers and professionals. These areas should be close to the work area, but with sufficient distance to allow people to work without undue distraction.

Physical testing areas These areas provide a permanent location for regular physical tests such as pH meters and viscometers. **Standard Pilot Plant Equipment Footprint** The third area is the Lost factory area Which houses the equipment Needed to produce all types of pharmaceutical materials. Equipment should be of various sizes known to represent production capacity.

Storage areas should be reserved for the storage of active ingredients and additives. These should also be divided into approved and non-certified areas according to GMP.

Requires ample storage space to store in-process data, finished products from pilot plants, and Production and test performance data.

Formulation Review:

A complete formulation review is important and should be done early in the scale-up process. The purpose of each component and its contribution to the final product produced by the small test equipment must be understood. It may then be faster to predict the proliferation of equipment use that will cause different types of stress or to detect them when they actually occur.

Contents:

One of the responsibilities of the cultivation business is to approve and use raw materials and raw materials in pharmaceutical products These are necessary because the raw materials used in small experiments may not be representative of the large-scale materials used in large-scale production.

Although all measurements have been performed, large quantities of these components may vary in size, shape or structure, resulting in different properties or differences in density, electrostatic charge and electrostatic charge. Resolution, streaming properties, color, etc.

Operational equipment:

Equipment should also be taken into account during subsequent scaling. Based on knowing the features of the products, it is accepted to evaluate the cheapest, most useful, most useful and most capable products among the products on the market.

Fig.2 continuous processing equipment

Productivity:

Current and future market needs should be taken into account when deciding on production equipment. The size of the device must be suitable for its intended use.

Development process:

In the past, products were expanded. The plan was created, the production process planned, and production equipment was reviewed, selected, configured, and debugged. The next step is to analyze the process and improve its effectiveness based on this evaluation.

The following items should be checked:

- Stirring speed
- Stirring speed
- Heating and cooling costs
- Filter size (liquid)
- Size (product)
- Drying temperature
- Drying time

Understanding the impact of the main process parameters on the process and the finished product forms the basis of optimization and analysis.

Preparation of Main Manufacturing Procedure:

- Chemical weighing table. It should identify the chemicals that will be present in the batch and state their quantities and the order in which they are used.
- Sampling direction. Work in process and finished products.
- Developing instructions should be in a language that employees can understand, called SOP.
- The data sheet must include Specifications regarding addition, mixing time, mixing speed, heating and cooling rates, and temperature.
- Must keep appropriate records. Issues GMP elements that should be part of testing are:
- Product conformance
- Process verification
- Planning regular preventive maintenance
- Methods for interim and re-inspection of work. Has been changed.

Change the analysis process to ensure quality assurance. The analysis method developed in the study should be submitted to the Quality Department.

Methods of change include:

- System review to ensure appropriate measurement tools are in place.
- Personnel must be trained to perform the test. □ The reliability of the test should be checked.

Tablet Pilot Plant Design:

When scaling tablet production from pilot Laboratory batch scale to medium and large scale Production, the same good judgment must be made at all business levels. The following are typical processes involved in the production of packaging materials.

Drying:

The most common drying method for drying pellets is still a hot air oven heated by steam or electricity. The main considerations to take into account as part of the kiln drying test are air flow, temperature and the pelleting depth of the chamber. If the granulation is too deep or dense the drying process will not be effective and if the dyes are affected the color will be carried to the surface of the granules. The temperature and air flow drying time must be determined for each product and each specific load. The main points to consider as part of evaluating the dryer are optimum load, flow, air flow, inlet temperature and humidity

Fig.3 Hammer mill

CONCLUSION:

Pilot plant scaling technology is an essential and important part of today's business world. In this concluding section, we discuss several key aspects of AI technology, its many benefits, and the role it plays in driving innovation, sustainability, and job growth in highways. First of all, pilot plant scale-up technology acts as a bridge between theoretical ideas developed in the laboratory and their practical use in the market. It provides flexibility and control from small trials to mass production, reducing risks associated with measurement processes without requiring prior validation.

This approach minimizes the possibility of failure and maximizes resource utilization. One of the key benefits of pilot plant scale-up technology is the ability to adjust the process. Using the middleware, researchers and designers can fix bugs, resolve issues, and discover changes that would not occur in the test environment. This iterative process of testing and modification results in a final product or process that is not only reliable but also better. In conclusion, pilot plant scaleup technology is an important tool to bridge the gap between laboratory testing and full-scale research.

Large-scale industrial production its importance extends everywhere from reducing and optimizing risk to fostering innovation, promoting sustainability and stimulating economic growth.

Businesses that use pilot plants to make technology more energy efficient can make progress and change the global landscape, ensuring progress, work and success for the year to come.

References:

- [1] Leon Lachlan, Herbert A. Lieberman. Joseph L. Nonindustrial Pharmaceutical Theory, 3rd Edition 1987 Bombay, Shoo 23, Pilot Plant Scaling Technology, Nylon 681 – 710.
- [2] Vanish. Doable et al, Kiev Them Cho Tinsels no haul Kiev Piloting Factory Scaling Technologies – Kiev Ntsuam Yeas, Indo-American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, Lob Pages – 1061 – 1066
- [3] P. Ramsubramaniyan et al., Pilot Plant Scaling Solid Dosage Form Technology – Tablet Overview, World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, Publication date – August 2014, Volume 3, Issue 8, p. –925 – 931
- [4] Art. Karol Islam, Conference on “Pilot Plant Scaling Techniques”, University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
- [5] Mantras. Pilot plant amplification technology http; M.Author flow. Co presentation subhrajit – 1080862 –Scaling up of pilot plant/ (mosaic 8 December 2019)
- [6] Kama Chaudhary, AC Rani, Rani Baal, Nitrate Seth, Comment: Scaling up of tablet production Scaling up with this method : a Forward Discussion, Int. Journal of Pharmacy. And creatures. Science 2012; 2(3): 223 – 239.
- [7] Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, Remington, “Pharmaceutical Science and Practice”, 21st Edition, 2008; 900 – 901.
- [8] Mike, Techceuticals, Solutions for Pharmaceutical and Nutria Manufacturers since 1989™, March 9, 2009.
- [9] Faure P, York RC, Method control and installation Wet granulation process for pharmaceuticals: a review, European Pharmaceutical and Biopharmaceuticals Journal, 52, 2001, 269-277.
- [10] levier, Analysis of fluidized bed parameters affecting different products, Anil Menno, Narinder Dhodi, William Mandela, Sibuchakrabarti, International Journal of Pharmacy, Volume 140, Issue 2, 30 August, p. 92-102.
- [11] Vyas SP, Hal RK. Controlling drug distribution: Strategies and advances. To change. Vallabhprakashan, 2002, 156-189.
- [12] Share L, Yu ABC. Update pharmaceutical products In Applications Biopharmaceutical and Pharmacokinetics. Fourth edition. McGraw-Hill, 1999; 169-171.
- [13] Ratner BD, Kwok C. Characteristics of distribution, surface analysis and controlled release. In: Encyclopaedia of Controlled Drug Distribution, vol. Published by John Wiley & Sons. In 1999; 349-362.
- [14] Nadia GD, Suede KD. Control of Release from Oral Tablets, Design, Collection and Processing 2003, 10 –16.
- [15] Malamutes S, Karidas T, Goidas P. Effect of particle size and adsorbed moisture on the compression behavior of certain hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC) polymers, Into J Pham 1994, 103, 205-215.
- [16] Gomel MC, Parikh RK, Paschal MN, Jena GD. Special compressible tablets Formulation and optimization of isoniazid sustained-release matrix tablets, Into J Pharmacy 2007, 640 – 644.
- [17] Levine M, Palmer F, Raja – Siahboomi A Study on directly compressible met forming HCl LI-based 500 mg sustained-release formulation, Controlled Release Society Annual Meeting 2005, 1 – 3
- [18] Jonathan, Buford, “Drug Development and Marketing Physicochemical Properties in Drugs, Processes and Granulation Fluid Bed Top Spray Mannitol mechanism Granulator”, 2005,

IJRTI